

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CATTLE CORPORATION VILLAGE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM (CASE STUDY OF THE BABULU BRAHMAN JAYA LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION)

By:

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Abstract:

This research aims to evaluate the implementation performance achievements of the Babulu Brahman Jaya livestock breeder corporation in the first year based on indicators of corporate performance achievements which include breeding and production aspects, feed aspects, animal health aspects, veterinary public health aspects, and processing and marketing aspects of livestock products. This research took place from July 2023 to May 2024. Location selection was carried out deliberately (purposive sampling). Meanwhile, sampling uses (proportionate random sampling) in 5 villages, namely: Kelompok Tani Petani Maju, Labangka Barat Village, Kelompok Tani Mugirejo Mandiri, Babulu Darat Village, Kelompok Tani Lestari, Gunung Intan Village, Kelompok Tani Karya Utama, Gunung Mulia Village and Kelompok Tani Sumber Mulyo, Gunung Makmur Village, members of the Babulu Brahman Jaya Livestock Production Cooperative in the Babulu District, Penajam Paser Utara Regency, East Kalimantan. Primary data was obtained from direct interviews with members of the Babulu Brahman Jaya Livestock Production Cooperative who were assisted with a list of questions (questionnaire) and direct observation in the field. This aims to determine the condition of the research object, as well as to obtain clear information about the respondent's condition. Secondary data was obtained from agencies related to this research, such as the East Kalimantan Department of Livestock, and Statistics of East Kalimantan. The research results show that the performance achievement of the Babulu Brahman Jaya cooperative is 80.52% (effective) while the score on the breeding and production indicator is 2,081, which is in the high category, the score on the feed indicator is 1,331, which is in the high category, the score on the animal health indicator is 1,810, which is in the high category, the score on the veterinary health indicator is 397, which is in the medium category, the score on the indicator management and marketing of 1,497 livestock products is in the low category. Performance achievement of breeding and production indicators is 93% (very effective), performance achievement of feed indicators is 85.32% (effective), performance achievement of livestock health indicators is 96.11% (very effective), performance achievement of veterinary health indicators is 67.86% (less effective), caused by a lack of awareness among farmers to protect and improve human physical, mental and social welfare, performance indicators for managing and marketing livestock products are 62.53% (less effective) due to the lack of functioning of the cooperative management function.

Keywords:

Evaluation, Performance, Cooperative, Beef Cattle

1. INTRODUCTION

Agricultural development through the development of agricultural areas based on farmer corporations is stipulated in the Minister of Agriculture Regulation Number 18/PERMENTAN/RC.040/4/2018. Farmer corporations are farmers' economic institutions with legal entities in the form of cooperatives or other legal entities with the majority of capital ownership owned by farmers.

The Ministry of Agriculture, through the Director General of Animal Husbandry and Animal Health, determined the group of beneficiaries of the Cattle Corporation Village development program and activities in North Penajam Paser Regency, East Kalimantan Province with Number 00080/Kpts/PL.130/F21.5/08/2021 dated 4 August 2021. To accelerate the increase in cattle population and beef production for sufficient animal protein, increase the welfare of farmers, and grow farmer economic institutions, efforts need to be made to develop cattle based on farmer corporations through programs and activities for the development of Cattle Corporate Villages in 2021. The groups that receive the benefits of this activity are farmer groups. Advanced Farmers in West Labangka village, Lestari farmer group in Gunung Intan village, Sumber Mulyo farmer group in Gunung Makmur village, Karya Utama farmer group in Gunung Mulya village, Mugirejo Mandiri farmer group in Babulu Darat village, Babulu sub-district.

The livestock corporation developed in North Penajam Paser Regency is the result of the growth and development of the Corporate Area Management Unit, namely in the form of a cooperative called the Babulu Brahman Jaya Cooperative. The implementation of the Cattle Corporate Village program is regulated by binding all groups into one corporate management with the formation of the "Babulu Brahman Jaya" Cooperative which will coordinate from upstream to downstream with the common goal of developing the Cattle Corporate Village business for the welfare of all members who are breeders in all recipient groups.

The Corporate Area Management Unit together with companions determines the preparation of an action plan known to the Provincial and District Regional Services. Preparation of a business plan as a reference in developing a joint business (collective business) which is managed under one management. The action plan is an operational plan document for the development of Agricultural Areas at the Regency/City level which is a detailed explanation of the master plan to direct the implementation of the development and development of Agricultural Areas at the Regency/City level.

The action plan is prepared simultaneously between the district office, corporations, and the Provincial Livestock Service by involving competent parties such as universities for 5 years in the context of structuring the economic institutions of corporate-based breeders with legal entities, integration activities from upstream to downstream of the livestock products produced, structuring an efficient and fair supply chain for breeders and developing marketing, developing livestock area businesses, accessibility to financing and insurance institutions, developing investment and partnerships and increasing human resource competency.

The main function of the Corporate Area Management Unit as the center for business management or corporate business of livestock breeders is to play at least a role in preparing business plans, implementing corporate business, production planning, determining production and product standards, market development, capital, business networks, partnerships, information, and technology and others.

Livestock corporation performance indicators by the technical guidelines for the 2021 Cattle Corporate Village activity program include 5 aspects, namely: (1) breeding aspect; (2) feed aspect; (3) animal health, (4) veterinary public health, and (5) processing and marketing of livestock products.

Referring to the activities carried out in the first year by the Babulu Brahman Jaya Livestock Cooperative, it is necessary to evaluate corporate performance to ensure the level of success/value by comparing the realization against the plans or standards and target parameters that have been set. The results of the assessment will be used as a corporate benchmark in terms of decision-making by both the government and corporate members in developing business plans and efforts to resolve problems.

The research aims to evaluate the implementation performance achievements of the Babulu Brahman Jaya breeder corporation in the first year based on indicators of corporate performance achievements.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

2.1. Time and Place

The research was carried out in July – September 2023 in 5 villages in Babulu District, North Penajam Paser Regency, East Kalimantan Province.

2.2. Method of Collecting Data

The data collected in this research consists of (a) primary data is data obtained from direct observations and interviews assisted by a list of questions (questionnaire); and (2) secondary data is data obtained from agencies related to this research, such as the East Kalimantan Province Livestock Service and the East Kalimantan Province Central Statistics Agency.

2.3. Determination of Location and Sampling Method

Determining the location of the research was carried out using purposive sampling, namely deliberately in 5 villages, the Tanjung Maju farmer group, West Labangka Village, the Mugirejo Mandiri farmer group, Babulu Darat Village, the Lestari farmer group, Gunung Intan Village, the Karya Utama farmer group, Gunung Mulia Village and the Sumber farmer group. Mulyo, Gunung Makmur Village, which is a member of the Babulu Brahman Jaya Livestock Business Cooperative in Babulu District.

The sample determination in this study was carried out using Proportionate Random Sampling with an error rate of 10%. To determine the sample for each group of breeders, first determine the population of breeders in each group, then determine the sample proportionally. This means that all members have the same opportunity to be sampled according to their proportions (Sugiyono, 2014). The number of samples was determined based on the Slovin formula (Silalahi, 2015), namely:

$$n = \frac{N}{N(d)^2 + 1}$$

Information: n = sample; N = population; and $d = 10\%$ precision value

Based on calculations, a target sample of 65 respondents in the 5 member villages of the Babulu Brahman Jaya corporation, Babulu District, can be obtained.

Then, to determine the sample size for each sub-population/group can be determined using the formula:

$$n_i = \frac{N_i}{N} \times n$$

Information: n_i = Number of samples from the i -th subpopulation; N_i = Sample population from the i -th subpopulation; n = Number of samples; and N = Number of population.

Based on this formula, the proportional number of samples taken from the 5 member villages of the Babulu Brahman Jaya corporation is as follows: the Advanced Farmer group with 17 respondents; Mugirejo Mandiri group with 9 respondents; The Sustainable Group consisted of 15 respondents; the Karya Utama group had 16 respondents, and the Sumber Mulyo group had 8 respondents.

Sampling was based on sub-populations of farmer groups using convenience sampling techniques (spontaneous data), namely taking respondents who were easy to find and could act as respondents (Nazir, 2009).

2.4. Methods and Data Analysis

This research is a case study, the data collected in this research was analyzed using qualitative descriptive methods. The categories given in corporate performance research consist of three, namely: low, medium, and high, that is, by breaking down these indicators into several question items, scores are given according to the respondent's choice, namely 3 = high, 2 = medium, and 1 = low.

To determine the realization of corporate performance, this is done by comparing the achievements of performance indicators with the maximum score of corporate performance indicators in the first year. The value of each corporate performance indicator target achievement is mathematically formulated as follows:

$$\text{Performance Realization} = \frac{\text{Achievement score per performance indicator item}}{\text{Total score per performance indicator item}} \times 100\%$$

To determine corporate performance achievements, this is done by comparing the realization of corporate performance for each indicator with the corporate performance targets that have been previously set. Mathematically, corporate performance achievements can be formulated as follows:

$$\text{Performance Achievement} = \frac{\text{Performance indicator realization}}{\text{Performance indicator target}} \times 100\%$$

If the performance achievement value reaches 100% or more then corporate performance is achieved, if the corporate performance achievement value is less than 100% then performance achievement is not achieved. Handayani (2020) stated that the criteria used in measuring the average level of effectiveness of the performance of each indicator in the Babulu Brahman Jaya corporation are as follows: < 60% (not effective); 60-69.99% (less effective); 70-79.99% (quite effective); 80-89.99% (effective); and 90-100% (very effective).

2.5. Determining Categories for Each Corporate Performance Indicator

Overall corporate performance measurement is based on target performance indicators. Determining categories for overall corporate performance is the same as determining categories for each corporate performance indicator. According to Nova S. Samual *et al* (2015), the score range for each corporate performance indicator is obtained using the following formula:

$$\frac{\text{Highest score} - \text{Lowest score}}{\text{Number of categories}} = \text{Range (class width)}$$

The highest score is obtained by multiplying the highest score value by the number of categories, while the lowest score is obtained by multiplying the lowest score value by the number of categories. Based on this formula,

- (1) To find out the score range categories for the breeding and production aspect indicators are as follows: 845-1,408 (low category); 1,409-1,971 (medium category); 1,972-2,535 (high category).
- (2) To find out the score range categories for feed indicators are as follows: 520-867 (low category); 868-1,213 (medium category); and 1,214-1,560 (high category).
- (3) To find out the score range categories for animal health indicators are as follows: 715-1,191 (low category); 1,192-1,668 (medium category); and 1,669-2,145 (high category).
- (4) To find out the score range categories for veterinary health indicators are as follows: 195-325 (low category); 326-445 (medium category); and 446-585 (high category).
- (5) Find out the score range category for the Livestock Product Management and Marketing range indicator is as follows: 1,040-1,733 (low category); 1,734-2,426 (medium category); and 2,427-3,120 (high category).
- (6) To find out the score range category for each indicator item is as follows: 65-109 (low category); 110-153 (medium category); and 154-195 (high category).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. General Description of the Babulu Brahman Jaya Cooperative

The Babulu Brahman Jaya Cooperative is one of the Village Development activities of the Cattle Corporation together with 8 other regions throughout Indonesia by empowering the community to encourage community economic growth so that community welfare increases. The development location is in Babulu District covering 5 groups in five villages. This farmer group together plays an active role in both breeding and fattening activities.

3.2. General Description of Respondents

General description of respondents based on descriptive data of respondents, namely as follows:

1. Characteristics of respondents based on age are as follows: < 31 years, 9 respondents (13.85%); 31-40 years old were 16 respondents (24.62%); 41-50 years old were 29 respondents (44.625%); 51-60 years old were 8 respondents (12.31%); and >60 years as many as 3 respondents (4.62%).
2. Characteristics of respondents based on education level are as follows: elementary school with 28 respondents (43.08%); There were 17 respondents in middle school (26.15%) and 20 respondents in high school (30.77%).
3. Characteristics of respondents based on the number of livestock owned are as follows: 5 animals, 22 respondents (33.85%); 5-8 individuals as many as 25 respondents (38.46%); 9-12 individuals were 14 respondents (21.54%) and > 12 individuals were 4 respondents (6.15%).
4. Characteristics of respondents based on farming experience are as follows: <5 years, 55 respondents (84.62%); 6-10 years as many as 4 respondents (38.46); 11-15 years was 1 respondent (1.54%); 16-20 years as many as 4 respondents (4.62%); and >20 years as many as 2 respondents (3.08%).
5. The characteristics of respondents based on the use of waste in compost are as follows: processing waste into compost as many as 11 respondents (16.92%); and not processing waste as many as 54 respondents (83.08%).
6. Characteristics of respondents based on the length of time spent raising cattle are as follows: 2 hours/day as many as 4 respondents (6.15%); 3 hours/day as many as 2 respondents (3.08%); 4 hours/day as many as 41 respondents (63.08%); 5 hours/day as many as 10 respondents (15.38%); and 6 hours/day as many as 8 respondents (12.31%).
7. Characteristics of respondents based on main occupation are as follows: farmers, 51 respondents (78.46%); cattle breeders as many as 6 respondents (9.23%); workers as many as 5 respondents (7.69%); entrepreneurs were 3 respondents (4.62%).

3.5. Categories for Each Corporate Performance Indicator

3.3.1 Breeding and Production Indicators

The development of beef cattle requires regional-based grouping that is adjusted to carrying capacity as a model for future development. In North Penajam Paser Regency, Babulu District is the largest cattle breeding center in the Regency with a general business pattern in the form of a fattening business, apart from intensive breeding, with a corporate business development basis through the Babulu Brahman Jaya Cooperative. Scores on breeding and production indicators are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Scores on Breeding and Production Indicators

No	Indicator	Score obtained	Category
1	Livestock in the group receive mating services	178	High
2	Males are using INKA in the group	65	Low

3	Number of pregnant cattle (in %)	186	High
4	Each parent population is included in the sycomandant system	195	High
5	Number of livestock births	165	High
6	Increase/growth in body weight/Average Daily Gain (ADG)	156	High
7	Fattening period (month/year)	191	High
8	The existing colony/shelter housing system adapts to the infrastructure	195	High
9	Intensive livestock-rearing patterns	195	High
10	Joint or group cattle herd management system according to group management agreement	187	High
11	Livestock records are carried out regularly	174	High
12	Livestock weighing for feeder cattle is carried out periodically	120	Medium
13	Born animals, male and female, were weighed	74	Low
Total		2081	High

Table 1 above, shows that the breeding and production indicators that are in the high category are livestock in the group receiving mating services, number of pregnant livestock, each parent population included in the sicomandan system, number of livestock births, increase/growth in body weight/average daily gain (ADG), fattening period, existing colony/shelter housing systems adapting to infrastructure, intensive livestock rearing patterns, and joint or group cattle housing management systems according to group management agreements; while those included in the medium category are weighing livestock for feeder cattle regularly; and those belonging to the low category are available males who use inka in the group and the animals born, male and female, are weighed.

3.3.2. Feed Indicator

The feed potential in the cattle fattening and breeding business at the Babulu Brahman Jaya Corporation is integrated with food crops, plantations, and forestry, and is already leading to semi-commercial businesses. Scores on feed indicators are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Scores on Feed Indicators

No	Indicator	Score obtained	Category
1	Availability of feed at cattle fattening (males)	193	High
2	Availability of feed for livestock's daily needs	195	High
3	Availability of feed (HPT) for breeding (parents)	195	High
4	Providing additional feed to strengthen feeder cattle (body weight $\pm$ 300 kg/head)	168	High
5	Providing additional feed to strengthen cows (body weight $\pm$ 300 kg/cow) with BCS = 3	194	High
6	The number of drinking doses given to livestock	108	Low
7	Additional feed was given to strengthen the cows (body weight $\pm$ 300 kg/cow) with BCS = 3	126	Medium
8	Drinking dose given to livestock	152	Medium
Total		1331	High

Table 2 above, shows that the feed indicators which are included in the high category are the availability of feed in fattening cattle (male), the availability of feed for the daily needs of livestock, the availability of feed (HPT) for breeding (sire), the provision of additional feed to strengthen feeder cattle (weight body weight $\pm$ 300 kg/cow), and giving additional feed to booster cows (body weight $\pm$ 300 kg/cow) with BCS =3; Indicators that fall into the medium category are the provision of additional feed to strengthen parent cows (body weight $\pm$ 300 kg/cow) with BCS = 3 and the drinking rate given to the livestock, and indicators that fall into the low category are the number of drinking doses given to the livestock.

3.3.3. Animal Health Indicators

Animal health is all matters relating to animal care, animal medicine, animal health services, control and management of animal diseases, disease prevention, reproductive medicine, conservation medicine, veterinary medicine, and animal health equipment and feeds safety. Scores on animal health indicators are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Scores on Animal Health Indicators

No	Indicator	Score obtained	Category
1	Animal health services from health centers/health workers	169	High
2	Implementation of biosecurity on cattle farms	128	Medium
3	Facilitate biosecurity facilities and infrastructure in this group	110	Medium
4	Control of Brucellosis disease	192	High

5	Control of Anthrax disease	194	High
6	Control of Jembrana disease	195	High
7	Control of worms	163	High
8	Control of reproductive disorders	165	High
9	Controlling the death rate	190	High
10	Birth rate control	183	High
11	Controlling calf mortality rates	112	Medium
Total		1810	High

From Table 3 it is known that the animal health indicators in the high category are animal health services from health centers/health workers, control of brucellosis, anthrax, Jembrana, worms, reproductive disorders, control of death, and birth rates; those included in the medium category are the implementation of biosecurity on cattle farms, facilitation of biosecurity facilities and infrastructure in this group; and controlling calf mortality rates; and there are no indicators in the low category.

3.3.4. Veterinary Health Indicators

Animal welfare is all matters related to the physical and mental condition of animals according to the animal's natural behavioral standards which need to be implemented and enforced to protect animals from inappropriate treatment by people towards animals used by humans. Scores on veterinary health indicators are seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Scores on Veterinary Health Indicators

No	Indicator	Score obtained	Category
1	HR understands aspects of animal welfare (5 freedoms) and is supported by complementary facilities	157	High
2	Fulfillment of the implementation of animal welfare aspects on farms	115	Medium
3	Fulfillment of animal welfare aspects in transportation	125	Medium
Total		397	Medium

From Table 4 it is known that the veterinary health indicators that are included in the high category are human resources who understand aspects of animal welfare (5 freedoms) and are supported by

complementary facilities, and what is included in the medium category is fulfilling the implementation of animal welfare aspects on farms, and fulfilling animal welfare aspects in transportation.

3.3.5. Indicators for Management and Marketing of Livestock Products

To increase market access for breeders, facilities and infrastructure are needed as well as strengthening breeder marketing institutions. Facilitation of marketing facilities for livestock products is expected to increase marketing efficiency, increase market access, reduce the marketing chain (reducing the dependence of breeders on collectors), and improve the bargaining position of breeders so that the prices received by breeders can increase. Scores on livestock product marketing management indicators are seen in Table 5.

Table 5. Scores on Livestock Product Management and Marketing Indicators

No	Indicator	Score obtained	Category
1	Business management of a farmer institution with a legal entity as an institutional management center and collective business center that is managed professionally	67	Low
2	Strengthening farmer corporations with the formation of legal entity farmer economic institutions (cooperatives/limited companies, AD/RT, and ongoing management	65	Low
3	Institutions/corporations in managing asset consolidation under corporate management	72	Low
4	Institutions manage business units under cooperative management (congregational collective business) with SOPs determined by the cooperative	65	Low
5	Corporations in preparing action plans for synchronizing cross-sector programs and activities to support corporate-based regional development which are signed by the regent	155	High
6	Corporations manage business reporting that is updated, orderly, and transparent	85	Low
7	The corporation manages the increase in business scale (reported increase in population and increase in production quantities	76	Low
8	Cooperatives have access to manage the amount of financing and working capital which can be used to increase business scale or capital	98	Low
9	Animal waste that has been used as a source of biogas	67	Low
10	Bio-Slurry is used as raw material for solid and liquid organic fertilizer	66	Low
11	Animal waste has been used as raw material for fertilizer	162	High
12	Management of fertilizer business development	72	Low
13	Does the corporation have sales transactions and how are they managed?	75	Low

No	Indicator	Score obtained	Category
14	Sales of fattening livestock are based on live weight scales	154	Sedang
15	Marketing cooperation in the process of selling livestock and products (off-taker)	129	Medium
16	Carry out online market promotion and development	89	Low
Total		1497	Low

From Table 5 above, it is known that the management and marketing indicators for livestock products which are included in the high category are corporations in preparing action plans for synchronizing cross-sector programs and activities to support corporate-based area development which are signed by the regent and animal waste has been used as raw material for fertilizer; those included in the medium category are sales of fattening livestock based on live weight scales, and marketing cooperation in the process of selling livestock and products (offtaker); Meanwhile, those included in the low category are the business management of a farmer institution with a legal entity as an institutional management center and a collective business center which is managed professionally, strengthening the farmer corporation with the formation of a farmer economic institution with a legal entity (cooperative/limited company, AD/RT and existing management), institutions/corporations in managing asset consolidation under corporate management, institutions managing business units under corporate management (congregational collective businesses) with SOPs determined by the cooperative, corporations managing updated, orderly and transparent business reporting, cooperatives accessing management amount of financing and working capital which is used to increase business scale or capital, animal waste which has been used as a source of biogas, Bio-Slurry which is used as raw material for solid and liquid organic fertilizer, management of fertilizer business development, corporations already have sales transactions and how they are managed, and carry out online market promotion and development.

3.4. Analysis of Performance Achievements

3.4.1 Breeding and Production Indicators

Seed animal breeds are animals that have superior characteristics and are inherited and meet certain requirements for breeding, while animal offspring, hereinafter referred to as seedlings, are non-seed animals that have superior characteristics to be reared for production purposes. Table of performance achievements of breeding and production indicators in Table 6.

Table 6. Performance Achievements of Breeding and Production Indicators

No	Indicator	Target	Realization	Performance Achievements	Criteria
1	Livestock in the group receive mating services	100%	91%	91%	Not achieved
2	Males are using INKA in the group	3%	33%	100%	Achieved
3	Number of pregnant cattle (in %)	0%	95%	100%	Achieved

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4	Each parent population is included in the sycomandant system	100%	100%	100%	Achieved
5	Number of livestock births	0%	85%	100%	Achieved
6	Increase/growth in body weight/Average Daily Gain (ADG)	0%	80%	100%	Achieved
7	Fattening period (month/year)	0%	98%	100%	Achieved
8	The existing colony/shelter housing system adapts to the infrastructure	100%	100%	100%	Achieved
9	Intensive livestock rearing pattern	100%	100%	100%	Achieved
10	Joint or group cattle herd management system according to group management agreement	75%	96%	100%	Achieved
11	Livestock records are carried out regularly	100%	89%	89%	Not achieved
12	Livestock weighing for feeder cattle is carried out periodically	100%	62%	62%	Not achieved
13	Born animals, male and female, were weighed	100%	38%	38%	Not achieved
Average Achievement				93%	Very effective

Source: Processed Primary Data

Table 6 above shows that the performance achievements of breeding and production indicators which include the criteria for achieving 100% are indicators number 2 to 10, while indicators number 1 (91%), number 11 (89%) were not achieved; number 12 (62%) and number 13 (38%). The average achievement of breeding and production indicators is 93%. In indicators number 1 and number 11, the performance achievement was only 91% and 89% (the target achievement criteria were not achieved), however, the criteria for these two indicators were included in the very effective criteria, and only the performance achievement did not meet the 100% target. The failure to achieve indicators number 11 and 12 was due to some breeders weighing them and some not weighing them. The unit of measurement for feeder cattle is the tail with an estimated price of $\geq$ Rp. 12,000,000; and calf birth weighing is carried out by a small number of breeders because they do not understand the importance of weighing, especially knowing the daily weight gain (average daily gain).

Therefore, it is necessary to improve livestock rearing management, emphasizing the importance of simple recording, reproductive management which is closely related to injection mating or artificial insemination, and disease prevention.

3.4.2. Feed Indicator

Efforts to maximize ruminant livestock productivity cannot be separated from the availability of forage. The conditions in question include the quantity and quality of available forage. Forages that are suitable for humid tropical areas have high growth capacity. The weakness of tropical forage is that it is difficult to maintain high quality because the older the grass, the less nutrient content it will have (Reksohadiprojo, 1985). The performance achievements of feed indicators are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Performance Achievements of Feed Indicators

No	Indicator	Target	Realization	Performance Achievements	Criteria
1	Availability of feed at cattle fattening (male) 2.1 tons/4 months/head	100%	98,97%	98,97%	Not achieved
2	Daily feed requirements for cows are 18 kg/cow	100%	100,00%	100,00%	Achieved
3	Availability of feed (HPT) for breeding (parents) 5,500 tons/year	100%	100,00%	100,00%	Achieved
4	Providing additional feed to strengthen feeder cattle (body weight $\pm$ 300 kg/head)	100%	86,15%	86,15%	Not achieved
5	Providing additional feed to strengthen cows (body weight $\pm$ 300 kg/cow) with BCS = 3	100%	99,49%	99,49%	Not achieved
6	The number of drinking doses given to livestock	100%	55,38%	55,38%	Not achieved
7	Additional feed was given to strengthen the cows (body weight $\pm$ 300 kg/cow) with BCS = 3	100%	64,62%	64,62%	Not achieved
8	Drinking dose given to livestock	100%	77,95%	77,95%	Not achieved
Average Achievement				85,32%	Effective

Source: Processed Primary Data

Table 7 shows that the performance indicators for animal feed included in the criteria were achieved only in indicators number 2 and 3. In indicators number 1 and 5 with performance achievements of 98.97% and 99.49%, although they do not reach 100%, these achievements are included in the very effective criteria. Meanwhile, indicators no. 4, 6, 7, and 8 included criteria that were not achieved with performance achievements between 55.38 – 77.979%. The average achievement of feed indicator performance was 85.32%. Factors that cause this performance not to be achieved can be caused by: breeders never measuring the amount of drink given to their livestock, and farmers only giving additional feed when young pregnant heifers and the provision is irregular, meaning breeders provide additional feed if there is assistance from the government.

3.4.3. Animal Health Indicators

Animal health services include veterinary laboratory services, veterinary examination and testing laboratory services, veterinary medical services, and/or services at the Animal Health Center (Puskesmas). The performance achievements of livestock health indicators can be seen in Table 8.

Table 8. Performance Achievements of Animal Health Indicators

No	Indicator	Target	Realization	Performance Achievements	Criteria
1	Animal health services from health centers/health workers	100%	86,67%	86,67%	Not achieved
2	Implementation of biosecurity on cattle farms	26%	65,64%	100,00%	Achieved
3	Facilitate biosecurity facilities and infrastructure in this group	80%	56,41%	70,51%	Not achieved
4	Control of Brucellosis disease	1%	98,46%	100,00%	Achieved
5	Control of Anthrax disease	0	99,49%	100,00%	Achieved
6	Control of Jembrana disease	1%	100,00%	100,00%	Achieved
7	Control of worms	15%	83,59%	100,00%	Achieved
8	Control of reproductive disorders	3%	84,62%	100,00%	Achieved
9	Controlling the death rate	10%	97,44%	100,00%	Achieved
10	Birth rate control	30%	93,85%	100,00%	Achieved
11	Controlling calf mortality rates	3%	62,05%	100,00%	Achieved
Average Achievement				96,11%	Very Effective

Source: Processed Primary Data

Table 8 shows that the performance achievements of livestock health indicators which are included in the criteria are achieved in indicators no. 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10. Meanwhile, indicators that are not achieved are indicators no. 1 and 3 with performance achievements of only 86.67% and 70.51%. This is due to the lack of veterinarians serving livestock in the 5 farmer groups, and farmers are not yet fully aware of the importance of implementing biosecurity.

To prevent disease, sanitation of livestock, pens, and the surrounding environment is carried out. Livestock should also be given vitamins (B-complex), deworming medication, and vaccination.

Implementation of reproductive management is carried out through estrus detection, pregnancy detection, and the use of appropriate mating methods (Ngadiyono, et al., 2019). Puskesmas is the spearhead of animal health services and management that is well organized, easily accessible, and trusted by breeders, both on a community scale and on a commercial scale, within the framework of the institutionalization of veterinary authority towards Siskeswannas (Iqbal, 2011).

3.4.4. Veterinary Health Indicators

This veterinary field covers aspects related to food, including technology for raising or caring for livestock, preventing and eradicating disease, animal health services, and even the stage of processing products from livestock. Performance achievements of veterinary health indicators are presented in Table 9.

Table 9. Performance Achievements of Veterinary Health Indicators

No	Indikator	Target	Realization	Performance Achievements	Criteria
1	HR understands aspects of animal welfare (5 freedoms) and is supported by complementary facilities	100%	80,51%	80,51%	Not achieved
2	Fulfillment of the implementation of animal welfare aspects on farms	100%	58,97%	58,97%	Not achieved
3	Fulfillment of animal welfare aspects in transportation	100%	64,10%	64,10%	Not achieved
Average Achievement				67,86%	Less effective

Source: Processed Primary Data

Table 9 shows that all veterinary health indicators including the criteria were not achieved with the performance achievements of indicator no. 1 (80.51%), indicator no. 2 (58.97%), and indicator no. 3 (64.10%). The average achievement of work indicators is only 67.80%. This is due to the lack of management of solid and liquid waste on farms, regulation of human traffic in and out of cages for disinfectant spraying schedules, resulting in the possibility of disease arising which disrupts animal welfare; and animal welfare during transport is completely uncontrolled by the farmer. As stated by Mayasari, et al (2023), the implementation of animal welfare, especially in livestock raising in Indonesia, is considered not yet optimal.

3.4.5. Indicators for Management and Marketing of Livestock Products

The marketing subsystem is fundamental in realizing a sustainable and agribusiness-oriented livestock business. Market guarantees with prices that are profitable for breeders will automatically encourage breeders to improve the quality and production of their livestock so that they are more productive and competitive. Achievements of performance indicators for the management and marketing of livestock products are presented in Table 10.

Table 10. Performance Achievements of Livestock Product Management and Marketing

Indicators					
No	Indicator	Target	Realization	Performance Achievements	Criteria
1	Business management of a farmer institution with a legal entity as an institutional management center and collective business center that is managed professionally	100%	34%	34,36%	Not achieved
2	Strengthening farmer corporations with the formation of legal entity farmer economic institutions (cooperatives/limited companies, AD/RT, and ongoing management	100%	33%	33,33%	Not achieved
3	Institutions/corporations in managing asset consolidation under corporate management	100%	37%	36,92%	Not achieved
4	Institutions manage business units under cooperative management (congregational collective business) with SOPs determined by the cooperative	100%	33%	33,33%	Not achieved
5	Corporations in preparing action plans for synchronizing cross-sector programs and activities to support corporate-based regional development which are signed by the regent	100%	79%	79,49%	Not achieved
6	Corporations manage business reporting that is updated, orderly, and transparent	100%	44%	43,59%	Not achieved
7	The corporation manages the increase in business scale (reported increase in population and increase in production quantities	100%	39%	38,97%	Not achieved
8	Cooperatives have access to manage the amount of financing and working capital which can be used to increase business scale or capital	100%	50%	50,26%	Not achieved
9	Animal waste that has been used as a source of biogas	30%	34%	100,00%	Achieved
10	Bio-Slurry is used as raw material for solid and liquid organic fertilizer	30%	34%	100,00%	Achieved
11	Animal waste has been used as raw material for fertilizer	30%	83%	100,00%	Achieved
12	Management of fertilizer business development	30%	37%	100,00%	Achieved
13	Does the corporation have sales transactions and how are they managed?	100%	38%	38,46%	Not achieved
14	Sales of fattening livestock are based on live weight scales	15%	79%	100,00%	Achieved
15	Marketing cooperation in the process of selling livestock and products (off-taker)	100%	66%	66,15%	Not achieved
16	Carry out online market promotion and development	100%	46%	45,64%	Not achieved
Average Achievement				62,53%	Less effective

Source: Processed Primary Data

Table 10 shows that the performance indicators for management and marketing of livestock products which included the criteria were achieved in indicators no. 9, 10, 11, 12, and 14. Meanwhile, indicators that were not achieved were indicators no. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 13, 14, 15, and 16 with performance achievements ranging from 38.46 – 66.15%. The average achievement of performance indicators for the management and marketing of livestock products is 62.53%. The failure to achieve performance indicators for the management and marketing of livestock products is caused by several factors, namely (1) the management of the Babulu Brahman Jaya livestock business, each group is still independent, (2) the business units developed in the Babulu Brahman Jaya cooperative are

generally not yet developed because still focused on production, (3) cooperative institutions have not yet functioned in collective business recording activities, (4) there is no motivation to carry out solid and liquid waste processing, (5) Bioslurry is generally not used and is left alone, resulting in bioslurry storage tanks become full and damaged because they have never been cleaned, (6) the cooperative institution has not yet functioned in collective business recording activities, because currently updated recording is still at the livestock group level, (7) the lack of openness between the cooperative management and members is the cause of not business development, (8) breeders choose to sell their livestock themselves both offline and online without going through corporate management.

3.4.6. Average Performance Indicators

The overall performance indicator achievements of the Babulu Brahman Jaya Corporation are shown in Table 11 below.

Table 11. Average performance achievements for each indicator

No	Indicator	Average Performance Achievement	Category
			Very Effective
1	Breeding and Production	90,77%	
2	Feed	85,32%	Effective
			Very Effective
3	Animal Health	96,11%	
4	Veterinary Health	67,86%	Less Effective
	Management and Marketing of Livestock		
5	Products	62,52%	Less Effective
The average performance indicator achievement		80,52%	Effective

Source: Processed Primary Data

From Fable 11 it is known that the performance achievement in the breeding and production indicators is 90.77% (very effective), the performance achievement in the feed indicator is 85.32% (effective), the performance achievement in the livestock health indicator is 96.11% (very effective), performance achievement in veterinary health indicators was 67.52% (less effective) and management and marketing of livestock products was 62.52% (less effective), the average indicator performance achievement was 80.52% (effective). The results of the data analysis above show that Babulu Brahman Jaya's corporate performance is in the good category. However, veterinary health indicators and livestock product management and marketing indicators are still in the ineffective category due to the lack of awareness among breeders to protect and improve human physical, mental, and social well-being, performance achievements of livestock product management and marketing indicators and the cooperative management function has not yet been implemented.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1. Conclusion

Based on the research results, it was concluded that The Babulu Brahman Jaya Cooperative has performance achievements with good criteria of 80.52% (effective). In detail, the score on the breeding and production indicators is 2,081, which is in the high category, the score on the feed indicator is 1,331, which is in the high category, the score on the animal health indicator is 1,810, which is in the high category, the score on the veterinary health indicator is 397, which is in the medium category, the score In terms of management and marketing indicators, 1497 livestock products are in the low category. Meanwhile, the performance achievement of breeding and production indicators was 93% (very effective), the performance achievement of feed indicators was 85.32% (effective), the performance achievement of livestock health indicators was 96.11% (very effective), the performance achievement of veterinary health indicators was 67.86% (less effective), performance indicators for managing and marketing livestock products 62.53% (less effective)

4.2. Suggestion

1. Efforts are still needed to improve veterinary health indicators and livestock product marketing management indicators so that they reach the medium to high category
2. Efforts are still needed to ensure that the performance achievements of veterinary health indicators (less effective), and performance indicators for management and marketing of livestock products (less effective) become effective or very effective.

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